

HISTORY FOR NON HISTORIANS: ANALYZING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VARIOUS NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING MODELS USED IN SOCIAL MEDIA

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The rise of social media, particularly in the speed and quantity of data being transferred, has the potential to empower members of the public by facilitating their understanding of past historical concepts, whether to apply it to present day scenarios or to deepen their comprehension of contemporary problems and the root of their causes. Prior research on the impact of social media on “popular history” focuses on issues caused by both creators and users of “popular history” transmitted through social media such as simplification and dramatization of historical fact and the spread of misinformation. Here we undertake a detailed study of the algorithmic issues in spreading open data through social media, biases caused not necessarily by human social media users, but rather by the technological application itself. (More specifically, these technological “biases” can be described as human biases, simply exacerbated by the nature of the algorithms in the technological application. The applications considered here, however, do not have any inherent biases).

We focus particularly on social media algorithms broadly categorized under Natural Language Processing (NLP) machine learning because NLP deals with text data, the most common method of transmitting “popular history” to a general audience. Prior research mostly focuses on extracting information from social media sites, and then using NLP to process it, but here, we take a different approach. NLP is also used by social media sites to personalize one's experience. It is used in social media "search engines" (like Google Autocomplete) but mainly in personalizing one's social media "feed." The techniques we analyzed in the study (N gram, Bag of words, word embedding) are all used to generate new information given large bodies of text relating to a certain topic (Song and Croft, 1999). We took a "deep dive" into these techniques, considering the Python code used to write these algorithms, finding how bias in the bodies of information we feed the model can affect the work it produces. Ultimately, NLP is considered from a layperson/ nonhistorian's perspective instead of a historian's since we try to see the impact of these NLP techniques used by social media sites on the public's understanding of history.

To consider a more detailed methodology of the study, we started with an analysis of various NLP techniques used by various social media applications and features, such as N gram models, the “Bag of Words” model, and the word embedding approach (McCallum and Nigam, 1998). Using

probability distributions, we calculated the extent of algorithmic bias and then qualitatively determined the extent of the magnification of a human bias. Using our analysis of NLP models, we then predicted the impact that each NLP model had on the spread of human (whether creator or user) bias. The study finds that the word embedding algorithm works best for transmitting “popular history,” as it both minimizes bias and also prevents the magnification of human errors (both simplification and dramatization of history).

Attached here are the more specific results from the study and details of each of the three techniques used (Gale and Church, 1994). The corpus, the data fed into the models, was a large database of a few hundred pages, on basic world history, obtained from a publicly available site (<http://glhssocialstudies.weebly.com/world-history-textbook---pdf-copy.html>).

For the N gram approach, or Markov model approach, these are the prompts generated:

George Washington is... (N = 4)

The world war was caused by... (N = 5)

what are some challenge right now from history.. (N = 8)

today Edison's discoveries are relevant... (N = 9)

Alexander the Great conquered these areas in the year of 300 BC and... (N = 12)

Notice how the model varies depending on the N we input. The higher the N, the more accurate it is, but it also means a higher likelihood of the model just copying the corpus (Franz and Brants, 2006). Additionally, the model has no sense of grammatical correctness and will often output incoherent or repetitive prompts, especially when N is small (Kneser and Hey, 1995).

In the Word Embedding approach, each word is represented by a vector, also called “word embeddings.” Similar words have similar word embeddings, as their vectors will together have a higher dot product (“cosine similarity”).

In the Bag of Words approach, the order of the words in the document does not matter because the model instead creates a “bag” of words without regards to structure and order. We analyze how unique a word is in a certain document or across all documents and the next words are found using associations (similarity scores).

The concept of open data is one that has percolated its way into public consciousness in the realm of history (Goodman, 2006). This study could improve the NLP models used by various social media sites, ensuring a better understanding of history for non-historians. The intersection between artificial intelligence algorithms in social media and the spread of “popular history” through social media is a valuable field to study and understand, especially as the world of history goes more and more technological. The public’s understanding of history is also a crucial issue to consider, especially with the ubiquity of historical knowledge in the social media/ Internet age. Our study, by considering the issues facing the field of history through a technological lens, hopes to bridge the gap between public understanding and historians’ understanding of history (Moosmann et al., 2007).

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